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Agrophysiological Assessment of *Hevea brasiliensis* Muell. Arg. Clone IRCA317 Grown on a Large Scale in Southwestern Côte d'Ivoire

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Abstract

The breeding scheme adopted in rubber tree has three (03) main phases, the last of which is the large-scale clone field or CCGE. In order to test the agrophysiological performance of clones created in Côte d'Ivoire, a CCGE with clones IRCA317, IRCA321, IRCA323, IRCA416 and IRCA840 was set up and monitored for 18 years in southwestern Côte d'Ivoire, precisely in the Gô rubber estate. They were grown with clone GT1 used as reference control. Each clone was represented by 384 trees organized in Fischer blocks with four (04) repetitions. The trees were tapped half-spiral downward for 10 years and quarter-spiral upward for three (03) years. The parameters measured concerned trunk isodiametric growth, rubber yield, tree stand, latex physiological parameters and susceptibility to tapping panel dryness. The results revealed that clone IRCA317 was the highest yielding with an average rubber yield of 85 g/t/t, that is, 153% of that of the control GT1. Its average yield in kg/ha/year was 55% higher than that of the control. This clone was characterized by average annual increments of 10.6 cm/year in the immature phase and 2.5 cm/year during tapping. However, clone IRCA317 was found to be very susceptible to tapping panel dryness with 24.8% diseased cut length and a few cases of trunk deformation given the 10 stimulations applied to it per year. This clone, which has an active metabolism, must therefore be moderately stimulated in order to sustainably express its high rubber yield potential.

Keywords: *Hevea brasiliensis*, agrophysiological performance, rubber yield, latex physiological parameters, Côte d'Ivoire.

Introduction

Hevea brasiliensis is currently the main exploited source of natural rubber (Compagnon, 1986), the only widely cultivated, traded and prized species in the world (Archer and Audley, 1987; Kew Science, 2017) with better rubber (Archer and Audley, 1987). Its cultivation began in Southeastern Asia and now extends to several tropical countries including Côte d'Ivoire. Thanks to the combined actions of the State and stakeholders in the rubber industry, which are supported by research, Côte d'Ivoire has become the 4th producer in the world and the 1st African producer of natural rubber. Thus, from 100 tons in 1960, the Ivorian natural rubber yield has increased to 1 100 000 tons in 2021 (APROMAC, 2021). More than 80% of this yield comes from village farmers who are used to applying intensive hormonal stimulation regimes. Rubber research in Côte d'Ivoire began in 1956 with the Institute for Rubber Research in Africa (IRCA) by testing the adaptation to Ivorian climatic conditions of elite genotypes imported from other rubber-growing countries. Since 1974, this program has also ensured clonal creation and selection. The created genotypes are assessed in a three-stage selection scheme including the seedling assessment field or CES, the small-

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scale clone field or CCPE and the large-scale clone field or CCGE. Depending on the tests, one or two stimulation intensities were studied: the moderate regime and the intensive regime. The intensive regime with 10 stimulations per year was the one selected, when a single stimulation intensity was applied in a trial. This made it possible to keep only the clones having a physiological profile adapted to the high stimulation intensities generally applied by village farmers.

In order to test the agrophysiological performance of clones IRCA317, IRCA321, IRCA323, IRCA416 and IRCA840 created in Côte d'Ivoire, a CCGE was established in the southwestern Côte d'Ivoire precisely in the Gô rubber estate. These clones were grown with the reference control GT1 and monitored in the immature phase for 5 years and the maturity phase (tapping) for 13 years.

Material and Methods

Study site

This study was carried out on the site of the société civile agricole du sud-ouest (SCASO), former Société hévéicole du Gô (HEVEGO). SCASO is located in southwestern Côte d'Ivoire, between 4°40' and 5°30' north latitude and 6°20' and 7°00' west longitude, in the Bas-Sassandra administrative region, precisely in the department of San-Pedro. This department is characterized by dense evergreen humid forest type vegetation with an average annual temperature of 25°C. The average annual rainfall is between 1800 and 2000 mm with a relative humidity of 90%. The soils are of the highly desaturated and gravelly ferralitic type (Keli *et al.*, 1992; Brou *et al.*, 2005).

Plant material

The plant material used consisted of six (06) *Hevea brasiliensis* (Mueller Argoviensis, Euphorbiaceae) clones. Clones IRCA317, IRCA321, IRCA323, IRCA416 and IRCA840 created in Côte d'Ivoire were compared to the primary clone GT1, originating from Indonesia. Clone GT1, one of the most cultivated clones in Côte d'Ivoire, is used as a reference control in all experiments. It is a hardy clone characterized by moderate growth before tapping commencement and slow growth during tapping. Its average yield is compensated by its good homogeneity, its average susceptibility to tapping panel dryness and its relatively good resistance to wind breakage (CIRAD, 1993; Obouayeba *et al.*, 2000). Its metabolism is average, with average sugars. It responds well to stimulation and should be stimulated moderately (Chapuset, 2001).

Methodology

Experimental design and treatments

The experimental design used was in complete randomized blocks of six (06) clones (treatments) and four (04) repetitions, that is, 24 elementary plots of 96 trees each. Each clone was therefore represented by 384 trees. The planting density was 510 trees per hectare (7 m X 2.8 m). Tapping commencement for each clone occurred when on all the blocks, there were at least 50% tappable trees. A tree is considered tappable when it has reached 50-cm girth at 1 m from the ground. The trees were tapped half-spiral downward for 10 years and quarter-spiral upward for three (03) years. The tapping was carried out every four days, 6 working days out of 7 (S/2 d4 6d/7). The trees were stimulated intensively, in particular 10 times a year with 2.5% concentrated stimulating paste in downward tapping (S/2 d4 6d/7 ET2.5% Pa1(1) 10/y) and 5% active ingredient (Ethephon) in upward tapping (S/4 d4 6d/7 ET5 % Pa1(1) 10/y).

Measurements made

Trunk isodiametric growth

The vigor of the clones was assessed from tree trunk girth measurements. These measurements were taken at the start of the experiment and then, once a year, at the end of the physiological crop year using a measuring tape. They were made at 1 m above the ground for non-tapped trees and at 1.70 m for tapped trees. This made it possible to calculate the average annual increment which was expressed (cm/year).

Rubber yield

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Rubber yield was assessed per treatment. The coagulum, removed at the next tapping, was collected, weighed monthly (fresh weight, F.W.) and stored. The transformation coefficient, dry rubber content percentage of a given sample of fresh rubber, made it possible to calculate the dry rubber yield for each pattern. It was calculated from one coagulum sample per treatment. Each sample was weighed, crimped, dried at 80°C in an oven for 24 h and reweighed. The dry rubber yield was expressed in grams per tree per tapping (g/t/t) and in kilograms per hectare and per year (kg/ha/year).

Susceptibility to tapping panel dryness

The quick survey method by visual estimation makes it possible to determine the susceptibility of clones to tapping panel dryness (Van De Sype, 1984). For each tapped tree, a number was assigned, proportional to the tapping cut length affected by tapping panel dryness, ranging between 0 and 6. For each plot, the precise count of the health status of the trees was performed and the total diseased cut length rate (DCL %) was calculated.

Tapped trees stand

The number of tappable trees was assessed before tapping commencement. Then, an inventory of the number of trees was carried out at the end of each physiological year. Total tapping panel dryness (100% DCL), wind breakage, uprooting, etc. induce a reduction in the number of tapped trees per hectare and therefore influence the yield.

Latex physiological parameters

The most important latex physiological parameters, due to their involvement in the mechanisms related to rubber yield, were analyzed once a year, during the last quarter of each year, according to the "latex micro diagnosis" method. (MDL; Jacob *et al.*, 1988). These include the dry rubber content and the sucrose, inorganic phosphorus and thiol group contents of the latex.

- Dry rubber content measurement

The dry matter content of the latex was determined by weighing 1 ml of fresh latex in a 10-ml pill box, before and after stoving at 80°C for 24 h.

- Sucrose, inorganic phosphorus and thiol compounds assay

The sucrose, inorganic phosphorus and thiol group contents were determined from the TCA serum obtained after coagulation of the latex in trichloroacetic acid (TCA). These contents, expressed in millimoles per liter of latex (mmol.l⁻¹), were assayed by the anthrone method developed by Ashwell (1957), the method of Taussky and Shorr (1953) and the method of Boyne and Ellman (1972) respectively for sucrose, inorganic phosphorus and thiol groups. The interpretation of the values of the physiological parameters took into account the reference values defined by Jacob *et al.*, 1987.

Analysis of the data collected

The data collected was subjected to statistical analysis. Rubber yield, trunk isodiametric growth, stand, latex micro diagnosis and tapping panel dryness survey data were processed using IBM SPSS version 20 statistical software. An analysis of variance was performed and the level of significance of the differences between the means was estimated by Duncan's test at 5% threshold. For the comparison of percentages, the mean comparison test using the least significant difference (Lsd) at 5% threshold was used..

Results

Agronomic parameters

Tree trunk isodiametric growth

During the immature phase, the average annual girth increment of the 6 clones varied between 9.5 and 10.6 cm/year (Table 1). Clone IRCA 317 had an average annual increment (10.6 cm/year) significantly greater than that of GT1 (9.5 cm/year). It was followed by clones IRCA321 and IRCA840 with 10.2 and 9.8 cm/year. Clones IRCA416 and IRCA321 showed average annual increments that were lower and statistically identical to that of the control GT1.

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Average annual girth increments during tapping were lower than those during the immature phase. The average annual increment of the control GT1 (2.1 cm/year) was the lowest compared to that of clone IRCA410 (2.8 cm/year) which was statistically identical to that of clone IRCA317 (2.5 cm/year). The average annual increments during tapping of clones IRCA323 (2.4 cm/year), IRCA321 (2.3 cm/year) and IRCA840 (2.3 cm/year) were average (Table 1).

Dry rubber yield

Clone IRCA317 was the highest yielding of the five (05) clones assessed (Table 2). Its average yield after 13 years of latex harvesting was 85 g/t/t, i.e. 153% of that of the reference control GT1. Clones IRCA321 (59 g/t/t) and IRCA840 (59 g/t/t) showed a yield statistically equivalent to that of clone GT1 (56 g/t/t). The yields of clones IRCA323 and IRCA416 were intermediate (122-130% GT1).

Results relating to annual dry rubber yield per hectare showed a significant difference between clones. Clone IRCA317 was the highest yielding of the five (05) clones assessed with a yield of 2989 kg/ha/year representing 155% of the yield of the reference control GT1. The other clones showed yield levels equivalent to that of GT1 (Table 2).

Evolution of the stand of tapped trees

The analysis of the evolution of the number of tapped trees during the 13 years of experiment revealed an increase from the first to the fourth year for all the clones. Apart from clone IRCA416, whose number of tapped trees dropped significantly from the fifth year, the other clones maintained their stand of tapped trees above 460 tapped trees per hectare (figure 1). However, morphological observations showed that clone IRCA317 had protruding and persistent leaf scars on the bark which could interfere with tapping on regenerated bark. Also, on this clone, it was observed in a localized way, deformations (Brown bast deforming) on some trees (Figure 1).

Susceptibility to tapping panel dryness syndrome

The diseased cut length (DCL) rates expressed by the trees varied significantly from one clone to another and ranged from 8.2 to 38.6% (Table 3). With 36.8% diseased cut length, clone IRCA416 was the most susceptible to tapping panel dryness syndrome. It was followed by IRCA317 whose DCL was 24.8%. Clone IRCA840 was the least susceptible to this phenomenon with 8.2% DCL. The DCL level of the reference control was 13.7% and was statistically identical to that of the other clones.

Latex physiological parameters

The average dry rubber contents (DRC) of tree latex were very high regardless of the clone. They varied from 47.97 (GT1) to 52.97% (IRCA840) but were statistically identical to each other (Table 4).

The average sucrose contents of the latex of the clones varied between 7.01 mmol.l⁻¹ (medium) and 12.25 mmol.l⁻¹ (very high). Very high values were observed in clone IRCA321 (12.25 mmol.l⁻¹) followed by clones IRCA323 (11.67 mmol.l⁻¹) and IRCA840 (10.99 mmol.l⁻¹) which showed high average sucrose contents and statistically identical to that of the control GT1. The sucrose contents of clones IRCA317 (8.84 mmol.l⁻¹) and IRCA416 (mmol.l⁻¹) were average and significantly lower than those of the other clones (Table 4).

Clones IRCA321 (26.33 mmol.l⁻¹) and IRCA416 (26.05 mmol.l⁻¹) showed very high average inorganic phosphorus contents of the latex and statistics higher than that of GT1 (23.71 mmol.l⁻¹). The inorganic phosphorus contents of the latex of clones IRCA323 and IRCA840 were high and statistically identical to that of clone GT1. Clone IRCA317 (17.13 mmol.l⁻¹) showed an average inorganic phosphorus content of the latex and lower than that of the control GT1 (Table 4).

The average thiol group contents of the latex were very high in clone IRCA840 (0.93 mmol.l⁻¹) and statistically identical to those of clones IRCA321 (0.81 mmol.l⁻¹) IRCA323 (0.82 mmol.l⁻¹). Clones IRCA416 and IRCA840 recorded 0.82 mmol.l⁻¹ 0.75 mmol.l⁻¹ respectively; and these values were higher than that of the reference control GT1 which was 0.65 mmol.l⁻¹. With 0.60 mmol.l⁻¹, clone IRCA317 showed

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average thiol group contents in the latex and statistically identical to that of clone GT1 (0.65 mmol.l^{-1} ; Table 4).

Discussion

Clone IRCA317 was the most vigorous of the clones assessed, with an average annual girth increment of 10.6 cm in the immature phase and 2.5 cm during tapping. The average annual increment of the reference control GT1 was lower in the immature phase (9.5 cm) as well as during tapping (2.1 cm). This justifies the fact that IRCA317 trees have reached the tapping standard, that is, 50-cm girth at 1 m above the ground, 6 months before the control GT1. The latter is characterized by average immature growth and low during tapping (CIRAD, 1993; Obouayeba *et al.*, 2000). Vigor is an asset that can guarantee a more significant tapping cut length and earlier tapping commencement. Gomes *et al.* (1983) as well as Obouayeba *et al.* (1996) reported a positive correlation between tapping cut length and rubber yield. In the breeding scheme in Côte d'Ivoire, any clone less vigorous than GT1 is rejected. The average annual increments which were between 9.5 and 10.6 cm in the immature phase switched to values between 2.2 and 2.8 during tapping. These results corroborate those of Elabo *et al.*, 2019, who obtained average annual increments between 9.13 and 10.18 cm in the immature phase and between 2.25 and 3.80 cm/year during tapping. This could be explained by the fact that the tapping of rubber trees leads to rubber production, whose synthesis, which is high-energy consuming (Lacote *et al.*, 2010), competes with the tree growth. As a result, there is a diversion of part of the photosynthetic assimilates which would be allocated to the growth of the tree, therefore a reduction in the annual rate of isodiametric growth (Obouayeba and Boa, 1993; Gohet *et al.*, 1996; Obouayeba, 2005).

Clone IRCA317 was the most productive of the clones assessed. After 13 years of latex harvesting, its yield per tree (85 g/t) represented 153% of that of GT1. This testifies to its vigor but also to its intrinsic rubber-producing capacity. Its cumulative yield per unit surface area (2989 kg/ha/year) corresponding to 155% of the yield of the reference control, confirms the good keeping of its stand of tapped trees. Indeed, the stability of the stand of trees observed in this clone shows its low susceptibility to the main factors of stand reduction, including wind breakage (Hofmann, 1981). Also, the average level of sucrose content shown by clone IRCA317 reflects an increased use of sucrose, raw material for rubber production (Jacob *et al.*, 1998). This confirms its belonging to the fast metabolic activity class.

Moreover, despite its very high rubber-yielding level, clone IRCA317 showed an inorganic phosphorus content of the latex ($17.13 \text{ mmol.l}^{-1}$) lower than that of the control GT1 (23.7 mmol.l^{-1}). Eschbach *et al.*, 1984, indicated that the concentration of inorganic phosphorus in latex, which reflects both the intensity of energy metabolism within laticifer cells and rubber synthesis, is very strongly correlated with yield. The low thiol group contents (0.65 mmol.l^{-1}) and especially inorganic phosphorus ones shown by clone IRCA317 ($17.13 \text{ mmol.l}^{-1}$) could be due to physiological fatigue linked to the high intensity of stimulation of this clone. Indeed, Gohet *et al.* (2019) reported that clone IRCA317 has an active metabolism. Therefore, it should be stimulated moderately (Gohet *et al.*, 1996 and 2008). Also, Tupy and Primot (1976), pointed out that beyond a certain limit related to the metabolic activity class of the clone, the stimulation can cause the phenomenon of phytotoxicity which leads to a senescence of the latex-producing tissue. Clone IRCA317 therefore did not support the intensive regime of 10 annual stimulations which was applied to it from the first year of latex harvest. The high rates of diseased cut length (24.8%) corroborate this assertion as well as the cases of deforming brown bast observed on some trees of clone IRCA317. This phenomenon due to a dysfunction of the laticifer system is considered as one of the symptoms of tapping panel dryness (De Fayé *et al.*, 1989, Jacob *et al.*, 1990). It can be caused by excessive tapping intensity or stimulation (Van de Sype, 1984), but also by the dry season and/or the quality of certain soils (Commère *et al.*, 1989).

Conclusion

At the end of this study, which was carried out in order to compare to the control clone, GT1, five (05) clones created in Côte d'Ivoire, it appears that clone IRCA 317 stands as a vigorous and high-yielding clone. Compared to the control, clone IRCA317 provides a rubber productivity gain of more than 50%. This clone was characterized by average annual girth increments of 10.6 cm/year in the immature phase and 2.5

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cm/year during tapping. However, its physiological profile does not allow it to withstand high stimulation intensities. It is, therefore, very susceptible to tapping panel dryness and sometimes shows trunk deformation. Clone IRCA 317 must therefore be stimulated moderately so as to allow it to best express its agronomic potential.

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Table 1. Average annual girth increments of trees

Clones	Average annual increment (cm/year)	
	Immature phase	Mature phase
IRCA317	10.6 a	2.5 ab
IRCA416	9.5 b	2.8 a
IRCA323	9.5 b	2.4 ab
IRCA321	10.2 ab	2.3 ab
IRCA840	9.8 ab	2.3 ab
GT1	9.5 b	2.1 b

In each column, the values assigned the same letter are not significantly different (Duncan's test at 5%).

Table 2. Average dry rubber yield over 13 years of latex harvest

Clones	Average dry rubber yield					
	g/t/t	% GT1	kg/ha/year	%	GT1	
IRCA317	85	b	153	2989	b	155
IRCA416	73	ab	130	2245	a	117
IRCA323	68	ab	122	2371	a	123
IRCA321	59	a	106	2074	a	108
IRCA840	59	a	106	2042	a	106
GT1	56	a	100	1927	a	100

In each column, the values assigned the same letter are not significantly different.

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Figure 1. Evolution of the number of tapped trees during the experiment

Table 3. Tapping panel dryness rate of rubber tree clones

Clones	Tapping panel dryness rate of trees (%)
GT 1	13.7bc
IRCA 317	24.8b
IRCA 321	15bc
IRCA 323	13.7bc
IRCA 416	38.6a
IRCA 840	8.2c

In each column, the values assigned the same letter are not significantly different.

Table 4. Physiological parameters of the latex of the clones studied

Clones	Physiological parameters of the latex			
	DRC (%)	Suc. (mmol.l ⁻¹)	Pi (mmol.l ⁻¹)	R-SH (mmol.l ⁻¹)
GT 1	47.97a	10.87a	23.71b	0.65c
IRCA317	48.64a	8.84b	17.13c	0.60c
IRCA321	49.88a	12.25a	26.33b	0.81ab
IRCA323	50.78a	11.67a	21.66b	0.82ab
IRCA416	48.93a	7.01b	26.05a	0.75b
IRCA840	52.97a	10.99a	22.99b	0.93a

In each column, the values assigned the same letter are not significantly different.

August 31, 2022

Photo 1. Trunk deformations observed in some clone IRCA317 trees